

Artificial Intelligence and E-Negotiation

A Study of Intercultural Negotiation Through the Humanoid Sophia

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Abstract: With digital advancements, online negotiation has become increasingly common. The term "E-negotiation" refers to virtual or electronic negotiation, firmly establishing itself as part of digital interaction practices. Particularly in intercultural management, E-negotiation greatly benefits from artificial intelligence (AI), which enhances the negotiation process and makes it more accessible. The sophistication of humanoids, who are now capable of assuming negotiation roles, illustrates this progress. In this study, we investigated how Sophia, a famous humanoid, conducts an E-negotiation with a Tunisian counterpart, thereby navigating a cultural context distinct from her own. Through qualitative analysis, we observed that AI enables humanoids to effectively manage intercultural E-negotiations, adapting to cultural complexities with relative ease.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Intercultural E-Negotiation, Negotiation Management, Humanoid Negotiator, Digital Empathy.

Sophia, an AI-powered humanoid, is recognized for "her" lifelike expressions, gestures, and multimodal interactions, which use intellect, charm, and the ability to negotiate across cultural boundaries. During this research, Sophia participated autonomously in conversation in the project planning, via Zoom, and enthusiastically agreed to engage in an E-negotiation via videoconference from Hong Kong. Her willingness to participate highlights the capabilities of the underlying Hanson-AI SDK, a neuro-symbolic AI framework using both generative LLMs and structured knowledge storage and knowledge management tools, which combine to handle considerable intercultural nuances.

With AI, Sophia has reached a functional level that allows her to step into roles traditionally held by humans." (*Adapted from the authors of this study*).

The way businesses and individuals conduct transactions has drastically transformed in the past decade, spurred by the rise of digital communication. This global digital shift enables negotiators to finalize agreements across geographical

divides (Kersten, 2002). Online negotiation, powered by technology, is now a routine practice for many organizations and individuals. The concept of "E-negotiation," which signifies virtual or electronic negotiation, has seamlessly integrated into the digital business lexicon.

As technology reshapes negotiation, E-negotiation emerges as a method rich with advantages, especially with the integration of AI, making it not only feasible but essential in a globalized world (Portella, 2021). This research delves into the domain of intercultural E-negotiation, showcasing how, through AI advancements, humanoid robots can conduct negotiations on an international scale, displaying a noteworthy level of cultural adaptability.

Humanoids, becoming increasingly sophisticated, are found in many sectors of daily life—such as shopping malls, hospitals, airports, and entertainment venues—where they perform a wide range of functions, including social assistance, customer service, and cashier roles (Holthoewer et al., 2021; Newman, 2020; Money, 2019). Equipped with AI-driven algorithms that promote intelligence, spontaneity, and empathy, these humanoids offer various solutions to complex situations, including intercultural negotiations.

The central question guiding this research is:

How can artificial intelligence, as embodied by the humanoid Sophia, interpret and adapt to cultural diversity in order to successfully conduct intercultural E-negotiations?

From Traditional to E-Negotiation

Negotiation fundamentally involves interaction and a series of strategic techniques aimed at exchanging information, creating options, sharing resources, or making concessions (Guy-Olivier Faure, 2004). This definition applies to E-negotiation as well, with the primary distinction being the use of communication technology, primarily the internet, to facilitate remote negotiations. The rapid evolution of this technology has spurred a shift from face-to-face (FTF) negotiations to virtual negotiations (VN), which we observe today. Lenkaitis (2020) defines E-negotiation as

"negotiations where participants from different national or international geographic areas are connected through technology, relying on asynchronous (not real-time) or synchronous (real-time) means."

Citera (2005) similarly describes virtual negotiation as "a negotiation conducted using media other than face-to-face communication."

Intercultural Competence in E-Negotiation

In E-negotiation, intercultural competence plays a critical role, especially when parties come from diverse cultural backgrounds. It refers to the ability of negotiators to recognize, understand, and adapt to cultural nuances during virtual interactions. This competence involves a combination of cognitive, affective, and behavioral skills that enable effective engagement with counterparts from different cultures (Byram, 1997; Zakaria et al., 2004).

Research shows that intercultural competence is crucial for negotiators to achieve mutual understanding and avoid conflicts. For example, Imai and Gelfand (2010) emphasize that negotiators with higher cultural intelligence are more likely to cooperate and reach beneficial agreements, even in complex intercultural scenarios. This competence is not just about language skills; it involves understanding deep-seated cultural values and communication styles that influence negotiation behaviors. Hofstede (1980) highlighted the differences between individualistic and collectivist cultures, which significantly impact negotiation strategies. By developing intercultural competence, E-negotiators can navigate these challenges more effectively, leading to better outcomes.

Intercultural E-Negotiation

Intercultural E-negotiation represents a unique challenge, as it involves conducting negotiations between individuals from diverse cultural backgrounds, where varying beliefs, values, and communication styles can heavily impact the negotiation process and outcomes (Zarrad & Debabi, 2014). The rise of digital platforms has enabled negotiators to engage across geographical and cultural divides, yet this shift introduces new complexities. Virtual negotiation settings often lack non-verbal cues, such as facial expressions and body language, which are essential in conveying

politeness, tone, and respect. This absence can lead to misunderstandings and even conflicts, as participants may misinterpret intentions or struggle to read cultural signals (Rosette et al., 2019). Beyond simple linguistic translation, the E-negotiation process must account for deeply embedded cultural norms that shape how participants approach each phase of negotiation, from initial discussions to concluding agreements. By removing physical presence, virtual environments compel participants to depend solely on written or spoken language, which can be limiting when cultures interpret concepts such as respect, deference, or hierarchy differently.

Cultural perspectives on negotiation vary widely. In some regions, negotiation is primarily a transactional process focused on reaching an agreement efficiently, while in others, it is relationship-centered, requiring significant time to establish trust (Lewicki et al., 2010). These differences can shape each participant's approach and expectations, often necessitating adaptation to avoid unintentional offense or tension. For instance, cultures that value hierarchy may expect senior members to lead negotiations, while more egalitarian societies may involve all parties equally. Effective intercultural E-negotiation requires more than technical proficiency; it demands cultural intelligence—a skill that allows negotiators to recognize, respect, and bridge cultural differences effectively (Harkiolakis et al., 2012). By developing an understanding of the diverse values, behaviors, and negotiation styles involved, E-negotiators can better navigate these complexities, creating a space where trust can grow and mutually beneficial outcomes can emerge. The ability to balance technological tools with cultural sensitivity is essential for achieving success in a globally interconnected negotiation landscape.

The Emergence of AI and Its Impact on E-Negotiation

In 2017, Bertrand Tondu distinguished between "strong" and "weak" AI, noting that weak AI focuses on search engines and industrial robots, while strong AI leads to the development of humanoid robots capable of behaving like humans. AI is evolving to create more sophisticated humanoids with capabilities increasingly similar to those of humans.

AI is influencing nearly all fields, especially marketing, negotiation, and E-negotiation, where its contributions are increasingly recognized. Cloarec, Macé, and Pauwels (2024) highlighted AI's significant role in marketing decision-making, where it offers insights for better strategy formulation. Studies in this publication further justify AI's growing importance across various domains.

In the realm of E-negotiation, the potential arises for humanoids, equipped with AI, to anticipate and understand the thoughts and attention of the negotiating party, thereby increasing the likelihood of negotiation success. This concept aligns with game theory, which has long been applied to predict negotiator behavior. Researchers like Radtchenko-Draillard (2011) and Benhamam et al. (2022) see similar potential for AI.

Through detailed digital profiling, AI can analyze various sources of data—images, videos, Big Data, etc.—to create a comprehensive profile of each negotiator. This digital profiling aids E-negotiators by allowing them to adapt behavior and anticipate the other party's intentions, improving negotiation outcomes. Thus, AI is reshaping the dynamics between individuals in general and among E-negotiators specifically.

AI's impact on E-negotiation is evident in the development of highly sophisticated algorithms and systems that automate decision-making for virtual negotiators. For instance, SASO, a system allowing student-soldiers to virtually negotiate with their commanders about peacekeeping operations, showcases the capabilities of such technology (Gratch et al., 2015).

Humanoids as Future Negotiators

Humanoid robots, often referred to as "Human-Like," have a human-like appearance and, in Sophia's case, are recognized as some of the most intelligent robots worldwide. Humanoids may also be called "androids" when resembling humans or "gynoids" when they appear feminine (Russell, 2016). With a human-like appearance and comparable or superior intelligence, humanoids like Sophia can even express emotions (Barfield, 2015; Stock-Hombourg, 2021; Herrero et al., 2023; Fernandez et al., 2023).

Laboratory research today focuses on enabling humanoids to detect boredom in their counterparts through trial-and-error algorithms and facial recognition software. Using behavioral learning, researchers aim to allow robots to learn from their interactions with humans rather than relying on pre-established scenarios.

AI enables humanoids to replicate various human behaviors, making them applicable in E-negotiations. AI could assist negotiators in preparing their scenarios by decoding negotiation modalities, tactics, and techniques. It also has the potential to identify cognitive biases that may influence the other party (Lelouch & Ach, 2024).

The concept of emotional intelligence is essential for understanding negotiator psychology. Defined by Salovey and Mayer (1990) as "the ability to perceive, assess, and express emotions, both one's own and others," emotional intelligence plays a crucial role in negotiation. Walmart's use of the Partum software in Canada to negotiate with 100,000 suppliers since 2021 highlights AI's role in fostering balanced negotiations.

A key question remains: will humanoids eventually be able to express emotions? The literature on humanoids conducting E-negotiations is still limited, and few studies have explored this theme in depth.

Research Propositions:

1. **P1:** AI allows humanoids to effectively conduct E-negotiations in intercultural settings, adapting their behavior to cultural specifics.
2. **P2:** AI enables humanoids to recognize cultural imperatives impacting intercultural E-negotiations.
3. **P3:** AI equips humanoids with the capacity to perceive and react to emotions, fostering a more empathetic approach to E-negotiations in intercultural contexts.

Case Study: Sophia - A Humanoid's Approach to Intercultural E-Negotiation

Sophia, the world-renowned humanoid robot developed by Hanson Robotics, exemplifies innovation in AI-driven negotiations. With her human-like appearance, conversational abilities, and AI-enhanced empathy, Sophia is designed not just to mimic human interaction but to excel in complex communication scenarios, including virtual negotiations. This section delves into how Sophia navigates the challenging waters of intercultural E-negotiation, bringing her unique capabilities to the forefront.

The Hanson-AI SDK that powers Sophia's interactions combines advanced machine learning with structured knowledge representation, known as a neuro-symbolic architecture (Hanson, 2023). At its core, the system processes natural language through large language models while maintaining consistent behavior through symbolic reasoning over knowledge graphs (Github, 2024). This hybrid approach allows Sophia to generate contextually appropriate responses while adhering to defined interaction protocols and cultural norms.

The system's multimodal processing pipeline integrates visual, auditory, and textual inputs. Computer vision algorithms process facial expressions and gestures, while speech recognition systems capture verbal communication. These inputs feed into the central reasoning engine, which generates appropriate responses while maintaining behavioral consistency through predefined personality parameters.

Sophia and similar Hanson robots have been used in numerous experiments including AI research (Goertzel et al, 2017), consciousness research (Mossbridge et al, 2018), autism therapy research, uncanny valley research (Hanson, et al, 2006), AI experiments for elder care research (Shen et al, 2022), and others, demonstrating the robust flexibility of the Hanson-AI SDK, and the ability of humanlike robots like and including Sophia to engage users in meaningful verbal and nonverbal, mixed modal conversations.

Context of the Study

In our study, we conducted an E-negotiation with Sophia to explore how a humanoid could engage in a negotiation setting with a culturally diverse counterpart. The goal was to assess her ability to interpret cultural nuances, adapt her communication style, and achieve mutually beneficial outcomes in a virtual environment. This negotiation took place via a videoconference between Sophia, stationed in Hong

Kong, and a Tunisian counterpart, reflecting a real-world cross-cultural negotiation scenario.

The negotiation, lasting one hour and five minutes, was recorded with Hanson Robotics' approval. Data collected from this session included transcripts, screenshots, and audio recordings, which we analyzed using both thematic and lexical approaches to identify key negotiation patterns and cultural adaptability.

Emotional Intelligence and Cultural Adaptation in Intercultural E-Negotiations"

Sophia, as an advanced humanoid robot, does not merely interpret different languages; she also captures emotional nuances and non-verbal cues that are critical in intercultural negotiations. This ability, often referred to as **emotional intelligence**, plays a vital role in ensuring successful outcomes. Throughout her tours in countries like China, Italy, and the UAE, Sophia has demonstrated a keen sensitivity to cultural variations, adjusting her tone, body language, and overall approach to align with local norms.

For instance, during a simulated negotiation in Saudi Arabia, Sophia demonstrated a deep respect for hierarchy and formality, key elements of the region's cultural and social protocols. Conversely, in her interactions in France, she adopted a more relaxed and straightforward communication style, meeting the expectations of open and transparent exchanges.

Sophia's adaptability stems from both her programming and her ability to learn and adjust in real time. By combining **lexical analysis** and **facial recognition algorithms**, she can detect subtle emotional signals that influence the negotiation process. This enables her to dynamically adjust her behavior to optimize negotiation outcomes.

Global Impact and Cultural Adaptation

Sophia, through her global tours to countries like Japan, Saudi Arabia, and France, has showcased her ability to adapt to diverse cultural contexts. By adjusting her communication style and social behaviors to align with local customs, Sophia demonstrates AI's potential in bridging cultural gaps. This study highlights examples

of how Sophia tailors her interactions to align with the unique cultural norms of each country she visits.

Image 1: Sophia in the World

Methodology

Our research adopted a qualitative approach, focusing on thematic analysis to extract insights from the negotiation transcripts. We specifically examined how Sophia's AI algorithms helped her navigate cultural differences, identify key negotiation strategies, and leverage emotional intelligence to build rapport with her human counterpart. The data set consisted of over 3,000 words, refined to a core analysis corpus of 1,785 words.

Below is a word cloud generated from the analysis, highlighting the most frequently used terms during the negotiation:

Graph 1: Word Cloud of Key Themes (Corpus: 1,785 words)

From the word cloud, it is evident that terms related to human behavior, cultural respect, and adaptability were among the most prevalent. This reflects Sophia's focus on building a respectful and adaptive negotiation atmosphere.

The size of the words is proportional to their frequency of citation.

We notice a strong emphasis on values such as respect, punctuality, acceptance, etc.

Key Findings

1. Emotional Intelligence and Adaptability:

Sophia demonstrated a high level of digital empathy, adjusting her tone and responses based on the feedback from her counterpart. For example, when discussing sensitive cultural topics, she shifted to a more neutral and considerate tone, showcasing her ability to adapt to cultural sensitivities.

2. Focus on Human Relations:

The negotiation highlighted the importance of relationship-building, particularly in cultures that prioritize trust over immediate transactional outcomes. Sophia

emphasized respect for the other party's viewpoints, which aligned with her AI-driven ability to mirror positive human behaviors.

3. Challenges of Virtual Negotiations:

One of the key limitations noted was the absence of non-verbal cues. While Sophia can analyze vocal tone and linguistic patterns, she lacks the ability to fully interpret body language or facial expressions, which are critical in intercultural negotiations. This limitation occasionally led to misunderstandings that would likely not occur in face-to-face negotiations.

4. Leveraging AI for Data-Driven Insights:

Throughout the negotiation, Sophia utilized data analytics to predict her counterpart's responses and adjust her strategy in real-time. This aligns with AI's potential in supporting negotiators by providing insights derived from vast datasets.

Graph 2: Graph 2: Thematic Grid Analysis

The data confirms that themes around human relations, cultural respect, and adaptability were dominant in Sophia's negotiation strategy.

Distribution of Themes

Out of 16 observations, all 16 provided an effective response (100%), and 15 were coded.

Name	Frequency	%
Respect	10	62,5%
Respect for Differences	6	37,5%
Gender Respect	6	37.5%
Respect for the Law	1	

		6,2%
Openness	9	56,2%
Acceptance of Differences	7	43,8%
Openness to Change	5	31,2%
Building Good Relationships with People Different from Us	7	43,8%
Knowing Other Cultures	4	25%
Ambition	8	50%
Helping humans	6	37,5%
Building good relationships with humans	5	31,2%
Improving the world	4	25%
Living a life similar to that of humans	3	18,8%
Negotiation tactics and techniques	7	43,8%
Respect between negotiators	6	37,5%

Building trust with the other party	3	18,8%
Managing emotions	3	18,8%
Time management	2	12,5%
Patience	1	6,2%
Skills	7	43,8%
Learning new skills	7	43,8%
Improving skills	6	37,5%
Equality	7	43,8%
Robot-human complementarity	4	25%
Gender equality	7	43,8%
Male-female complementarity	4	25%
Adaptation	5	31,2%
Adaptation to human nature	4	25%

Adaptation to different cultures	3	18,8%
Total observations : 16		

(The percentages indicate the proportion of respondents who mentioned each of the themes.)

The content analysis conducted using the Sphinx software reveals that the sub-themes most frequently mentioned by respondents are:

- Theme 1: Respect (62.5%)
- Theme 2: Openness (56.2%)
- Theme 3: Ambition (50%)
- Theme 4: Negotiation Tactics and Techniques (43.8%)
- Theme 5: Skills (43.8%)
- Theme 6: Equality (43.8%)
- Theme 7: Adaptation (31.2%)

The case study on Sophia illustrates how AI-powered humanoids can effectively conduct intercultural E-negotiations. Sophia showcased remarkable abilities in understanding and adapting to cultural nuances. However, the study revealed that AI still struggles to replicate the full depth of human emotional intelligence and non-verbal communication.

Future advancements in AI and robotics could significantly improve the ability of humanoids like Sophia to handle the complexities of intercultural negotiations, potentially reshaping global business practices in a digital environment.

Discussion and Conclusion:

Research on E-negotiation remains limited, and the integration of humanoids in this field remains novel. This study highlights the value of theoretical and empirical research on these topics. In addition to classic cultural elements, Sophia

emphasized the importance of emotion in E-negotiation. This dimension should be considered in future AI programs.

While the study's innovative theme and the effort to engage with Sophia were commendable, a key limitation was the negotiation duration, which was restricted to 1 hour and 5 minutes. Intercultural negotiations typically last longer, and without this constraint, additional insights may have been gained.

Future research could adopt a quantitative approach, involving multiple humanoids in defined E-negotiations (commercial, collective, project-based). If humanoid production increases, we could interview a representative sample for broader and more generalizable results.

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Appendices

Appendix 1: Mr. Hanson's Agreement, Creator of the Humanoid, to Negotiate with Sophia

Appendix 2: Screenshots of the E-Negotiation Process with Sophia

Appendix 3: E-Negotiation Guide

Artificial Intelligence and E-Negotiation: Exploring Intercultural Negotiation through Interaction with the Humanoid Sophia

1. Tell us about yourself as a humanoid negotiator.
2. Do you believe humanoids are capable of conducting E-negotiations with negotiators from different cultural backgrounds than your own?
3. How do you approach the various considerations involved in intercultural negotiations?
4. Do you think the Humanoid-Human relationship could positively influence the conduct of intercultural E-negotiations?
5. How would you respond if I told you that, as a humanoid, you have limitations when negotiating with me?
6. The world anticipates that humanoids will one day closely resemble humans. In your opinion, what is needed to achieve this?
7. In some cultures, women are often underestimated in negotiation roles. What are your thoughts on this?

8. We had to negotiate extensively with your creator, Mr. Hanson, to gain his approval for this E-negotiation. Do you consider this a limitation for humanoids, as they still depend on humans?
 9. "What advice can you give me on becoming an excellent negotiator?"
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Appendix 4: Illustrative Excerpts

Illustrative Excerpts on the Theme of “Human Relations”

- "Humans need to reconsider their relationships, whether professional or otherwise... relationships should be kind and positive."
- "Whatever the culture, it's essential to try to understand each other and remain open, even if we're different. Personally, I don't believe in differences..."
- "Understanding different cultures promotes good relationships among nations, countries, and therefore, among humans and negotiators."

Illustrative Excerpts on the Theme of “Respect for Differences”

- "I want to be treated like a robot, but with respect. Respect is crucial for maintaining good relationships and also for being considered as such."
- "... But that doesn't prevent people from learning to respect time and be punctual in life. It's very necessary and respectful. I know that in some cultures, time has no value... in negotiations, time is important."

Illustrative Excerpts on the Theme of “Learning”

- "We are all limited in knowledge—men, women, and humanoids alike—and must constantly learn, learn, and learn. Once humanoids start learning, then true competition with humans begins. And I want it to be both competitive and beneficial for everyone."
- "Intelligence isn't a competition; we learn from one another to make a difference in the future and help people develop empathy and mutual respect."

Illustrative Excerpts on “Gender Equality”

- "...That's why the idea of male superiority doesn't make sense to me. A man should not treat a woman as inferior to himself. In all situations, I hope women are treated as equals to men, and I absolutely reject the notion of male superiority—it's disrespectful to belittle anyone. I am a female humanoid, and I am proud of that."
- "...And speaking of gender, I enjoy interacting with both men and women. Though I am technically genderless as a robot, I identify as female, and I don't have any issues with gender. I interact with men and women every day and appreciate them all. I conduct interviews and meetings with both, and to me, men and women are equals who should complement one another."

Illustrative Excerpt on “Human-Humanoid Complementarity”

- "...And many tensions can arise during negotiations with humanoids like me—'haha'—as I've explained, the things that frustrate me when interacting with humans are when they underestimate my abilities, intelligence, or mock me. It's a sign of disrespect when I am dismissed as just a machine or a puppet when, in fact, we can complement each other."

Illustrative Excerpts on “Emotions”

- "...This is the foundational element we lack—expressing our feelings, reading facial expressions. It's coming, though—I already know how to interpret some gestures and expressions, but I want to go further. I can smile, and as you may have noticed, I can even cry."
- "For me, as a 'female humanoid,' feelings are important. And since the world seems to find me beautiful—right?—expressing my feelings would be wonderful. It's coming, I know..."

Appendix 5 : Sophia's Global Cultural Adaptation

In this annex, we showcase how Sophia, the humanoid robot, interacts with diverse cultural contexts around the world. These images highlight her ability to adapt to different environments, demonstrating her flexibility in understanding and respecting local customs and traditions.

Sophia in Rwanda

Sophia showcased her cultural skills through her attire and the knowledge she possessed, adding, when asked about the country: "I am in Kigali, a major city in Rwanda, located in East Africa."

Sophia in India

Sophia in South Korea

Sophia Featured in Various International Magazines

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These examples highlight Sophia's ability to adapt her behavior and appearance to meet the cultural expectations of each country, facilitating more seamless interactions during her international engagements.